

DESIGN AND CHARACTERIZATION OF FILAMENT-WOUND COMPOSITE SHELLS REINFORCED BY GRID

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1 General Introduction

Grid-stiffened polymer composite reinforced by the fibre has been popularly used in the aircrafts, owing to their potential technical advantages that compared with traditional aluminum alloy structure, less than 40% in weight for the same structures [1]. With requirement and technology increasing as well as fast developing, the further requirement of grid-stiffened polymer composite should be met for the light-weighted structure and low cost. Although grid-stiffened polymer composites have found a few applications, they have not fully reached their technological potential. Largely due to that the drawbacks of grid-stiffened polymer composites lie in infertile manufacturing and processing technologies, as well as simply method in light-weighted design. Another important issue is lagging development speed of low cost technology resulting from a short history of grid-stiffened polymer composites [2]. As a result, the development and application of grid-stiffened polymer composites is seriously limited.

2 Experimental Procedure

In this work, resin system is incorporated of an epoxy resin (TDE-85), which is famous for its high strength and temperature tolerance. The TDE-85 has three epoxy groups per one monomer, resulting in the epoxy value more than 85%. Based on the chemical reaction mechanism, the epoxy resin has been firstly modified by the Bisphenol F, to reduce the brittleness and cost, moreover to help the interface more suitable for the resin and fibre bonding. The ethylene glycol diglycidyl ether (EGDE) is used as the diluting agent and curing agent, respectively, in which the EGDE is introduced to improve the viscosity of resin system. The EGDE is used to reduce the viscoelastic properties of the polymer matrix. To prevent the

reactive properties from being reduced, the dilute agent containing hydroxyl groups has been used to react with the matrix at high temperature. Then the epoxy mixture with a fixed weight ratio of epoxy resin, dilute agent, and curing agent is cured at 100 °C for 1 hr, and ramped up to 120 °C for 3 hrs. Finally, the pre-cured sample is post cured at the temperature of 150 °C for 3 hrs. The T700 carbon fiber is used as the have been grid stiffened by the carbon fiber from longitudinal, loop, and triangle directions, respectively.

3 Results and Discussion

The various loading applied on the grid-stiffened polymer composite structures introduce challenges to the design process. It takes a great deal of effort to make a detailed finite element model and simulation for an advanced grid stiffened (AGS) structure that is made from the heterogeneous polymer composite. In the simulation process, the model should be simple, as well as concise. In this study, the grids in AGS structures are distinguished from the other substances by a combination of grid type and quantity. The design procedure consists of initial optimization solutions followed by detailed Finite Element Modeling (FEM) [3]. This process needs to be repeated until the design satisfies the performance criteria for the AGS structures. With these efforts, it is expected to find that the most optimum design for the AGS structures are stiffened with various types of grids. The finite element model allows the designer to obtain a more refined picture of how the structure will act under the applied loads. It also allows the designer to examine critically loaded areas in the structures such as attachment points for peripheral equipment, separation joints on the fairing, and loads at the intersection of the fairing and the vehicle. Figure 1 shows the Finite Element Model of AGS structure stiffened with triangular grids

showing deflection under synergistic effect of axial and side pressures.

Fig. 1. Effect of axially edgewise on the stabilization coefficient of cylindrical shell in response to synergistic axial and edgewise pressures.

On the other hand, the stabilization coefficient of the AGS structures stiffened with different quantities of vertical and horizontal stiffeners is measured when it is subject to axial, side, and a combination of axial and side pressures, respectively. As shown in the Figures 2, experimental results reveal that the stabilization coefficient of the AGS structures gradually increases with an increase in longitudinal stiffener from 0 to 18, 27, 36, and finally to 54. Taking the AGS structure stiffened with seven loop grids for example, the stabilization coefficient of the AGS structure increases from 1.1 to 12.852 with an increase in longitudinal stiffener from 0 to 54 [4]. These curves display a closed structure that contains vertical and horizontal grids reinforced with either the vertical or horizontal grid stiffeners. In addition, the longitudinal grid stiffener plays a more positive effect on the AGS structures in comparison with the loop grid stiffener seeing as how the structures are subject to an axial pressure.

4 Conclusions

The AGS structures that were developed for aerospace and aircraft applications would dramatically improve the capabilities of launch vehicles. This advanced polymer structure significantly improved the payload capabilities with almost no increase in weight over the existing fairing. This characteristic enabled the AGS structure to have a high mechanically resistive capability in practical applications. It also effectively

provided cost savings for each aircraft and spacecraft launch. At the same time, the fabrication process of this AGS structure was almost entirely automated, which resulted in cost savings of nearly 15% over other types of fairings. Successful design, manufacturing, and flight qualification of AGS structures provided a clear path for other programs and applications to follow as more efficient and cost effective structures are needed. Therefore, these advantages allowed the AGS structures and other advanced polymer composites to be used in more and more structures and systems, not only in aircraft and spacecraft structures, but also in civil structures.

Fig. 2. Effect of axially edgewise on the stabilization coefficient of cylindrical shell in response to synergistic axial and edgewise pressures,[4] ©Copyright 2011, RSC Publishing.

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